

Effects of Artificial Intelligence Package on Mechanical Technology Education Students' Academic Performance In Milling Machine Operation In Tertiary Institutions In Rivers State, Nigeria.

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Abstract- This study investigated the effects of artificial intelligence package on mechanical technology education students' academic performance in Milling Machine operation in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The aspect of Artificial intelligence investigated were perceived course mastery, research complexity and functionality. Three research questions were raised and answered, while three null hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A quasi-experimental design guided the study. The population of the study was 188 year 1-IV mechanical technology education students from three tertiary institutions in Rivers State that offers mechanical technology education programmes, year three with a population of 72 was sampled. The researcher collected data for the study using teacher made test. The instrument was validated by two lecturers in the department of Industrial Technology Education (mechanical technology option). The reliability of the instrument was established using test, re-test method. The data achieved were analyzed with PPMC. The coefficient achieved was .84. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistics were used to test the hypotheses at .05 levels of significance. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that experimental group taught with artificial intelligence package performed better than the control group taught with white-board. It was recommended that government should train lecturers on how to develop and use AI packages in addition to white-board (conventional) teaching method since it has proven to be effective.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence. Mechanical technology education, Academic Performance. Milling Machine

I. INTRODUCTION

All human actions are based on anticipated futures. We cannot know the future because it does not exist yet, but we can use our current knowledge and education to imagine futures and make them happen. Education is generally acknowledged as being crucial system of any nation. It is the art of acquiring knowledge, developing of the reasoning and judgmental abilities of the mind, character and manipulative competencies in a formal setting. Education can authoritatively be regarded as key to national development because it unravels economic potentials, strengthens and equips individuals in society to fully be engaged and benefit from national

polices. According to Agi and Yelloiwe cited in Edionwe (2024), education is important to development of human resources, impartation of appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes. Education plays an unquantifiable role in nation and the global world at large in terms of creating an environment of self-actualization

Several educational programmes and courses are offered in tertiary institutions in Rivers State one of which is machining (milling machine operation) in mechanical technology education. Milling machine is one of the most versatile conventional machine tools with a wide range of metal cutting capability. Many complicated operations such as indexing, gang milling, and straddle milling etc. can be carried out on a milling machine. Most of the milling machine

are constructed of column and knee structure and they are classified into two main types namely Horizontal Milling Machine and Vertical Milling Machine. The name Horizontal or Vertical is given to the machine by virtue of its spindle axis. Horizontal machines can be further classified into Plain Horizontal and Universal Milling Machine. The main difference between the two is that the table of a Universal Milling Machine can be set at an angle for helical milling while the table of a Plain Horizontal Milling Machine is not. Cutting tool used for milling includes slab mill cutter, side and face cutters, slitting saws, end mill cutters, rough cut end mill cutter, slot drills, involute gear cutter, etc.

Milling is a metal removal process by means of using a rotating cutter having one or more cutting teeth. Milling machines are widely used in the tool and die making industry and are commonly used in the manufacturing industry for the production of a wide range of components. Typical examples are the milling of flat surface, indexing, gear cutting, as well as the cutting of slots and key-ways. Cutting action is carried out by feeding the workpiece against the rotating cutter. Thus, the spindle speed, the table feed, the depth of cut, and the rotating direction of the cutter become the main parameters of the process. Good results can only be achieved with a well-balanced setting of these parameters.

When knowledge project that absorbs various information, analyzes these data, and studies the methods of expressing the outcomes requires immediate feedback, and collaborative activities, but further growth and improvement are needed, including training, accessibility, research, monitoring, and best practices sharing, Artificial Intelligence comes to mind

AI refers to the development of computer systems capable of activities typically requiring human intelligence, such as speech recognition, visual perception, decision-making, and language translation (Himanen et al., 2019). AI has emerged as an integral part of several sectors, altering the way businesses and personnel engage with technology, the manufacturing industry is undergoing evolution with the introduction of smart factories which are powered with a variety of AI technologies. For

example, these smart factories are integrated with tools that assist in automating processes, predictive maintenance, and implementing quality assurance systems to improve efficiency and minimize operational idle time (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). In the area of education, Artificial intelligence (AI) systems assist effectively in online learning and teaching, automating instructors' mundane activities; personalizing learning for students; and adaptive evaluation (Seo et al, 2021).

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) has made visible changes in educational processes and management in the last few years. This progression enables the educational model to be more multidimensional in terms of human, non-human, and their presence on the web. Martínez-Comesanã et al., (2023) posited that the potential offered by AI technologies has been proven in various domains, including intelligent buildings as well as learning spaces. Artificial intelligence (AI) has reshaped the education landscape, driving unprecedented changes in teaching methodologies and student learning experiences. Through data-driven machine learning techniques, AI can optimize learning outcomes, streamline pedagogical processes, and tailor educational tools to individual needs (Wang and Liu (2021)). The adoption of AI in education offers a promising pathway to personalized learning and improved academic performance

Academic performance entails the different means students respond to their academic materials assigned by their teachers/lecturers. This explains that high academic performance is directly connected and measured by the examination results. Hannan, and Liu (2021). Stated that determining a student's standing in a university requires evaluating their academic performance. Throughout a semester, this procedure helps decision-makers, academic staff, and educational administrators to accurately assess students in a variety of courses. It also serves as a warning to students to evaluate their performance and take the required actions to get better

There are two schools of thought on the definition of academic performance. The first group is defined

by Ashwin and Mc-Vitty (2015), who stated that academic performance refers to the numerical scores of a student's knowledge, which measure the degree of a student's adaptation to academic work and to the educational system. The second group of definitions is more subjective, and suggests that academic success is reliant upon the student's attitudes towards his or her academic achievement, and depends on him or herself (Khadivi-Zand cited in Coetzee, 2021). Academic performance is referred to as knowledge that is obtained by an individual during the academic period for a subject or group of subjects that one learns in an academic year such as a semester. From the foregoing, academic performance could be described as the achievement of students in an academic exercise.

AI applications include personalization of learning experiences, automation of administrative tasks, and provision of insights into student performance. Popenici and Kerr (2017) posited that artificial Intelligence is advancing faster in the services and educational systems. It is geared toward automated individualized education to support students' academic performance at all levels of education through virtual engagement at the student's convenience and time. Raja and Nagasubramani (2018) added that it is much more interactive, making knowledge transfer easy and convenient, demonstrating that reliance and dependency on this technology make life easier and smoother, among other things. It is based on this that the research work is focused on investigating the effects of AI on mechanical technology education students' academic performance in Milling Machine in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The value of education in human lives cannot be overstated in today's modern education because it enhances both human and material resources. According to Karmanje and Alhassan (2018), education was obtained one-on-one in the human history of civilization, using face-to-face direct teaching and learning techniques. There were insufficient instructional resources to support teachers in their teaching. Teachers and students made every effort to make teaching and learning

practicable, accessible, and unhindered. However, today's technology is increasingly used in teaching and learning (Kataria, 2018; Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). One technological advancement, artificial Intelligence (AI), has made considerable progress in becoming an essential component of the education sector. According to UNESCO (2021), fifty percent of worldwide organizations have incorporated artificial Intelligence into their day-to-day functions. Similarly, educational and training institutes teach their teachers and students the skills of artificial intelligence. The learning and education sector have witnessed remarkable advancements in recent years due to technological innovations. Internet searches have become an integral part of school learning, and tablets have increasingly replaced or supplemented traditional books in universities. Despite these significant developments, their impact may pale in comparison to the anticipated effects of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. (Ramo et al., 2022), Recent advancements in AI have led to a surge in educational applications, introducing new possibilities and challenges for teaching and learning in higher education. These innovations have the potential to fundamentally reshape the governance and internal structures of higher education institutions (Singh & Hiran, 2022) Student engagement is the key to academic success and well-being, involving active participation and investment in learning. Engaged students are motivated, achieve academic success, and remain in school. Classroom interactions fostering collaboration, critical thinking, and practical knowledge application enhance engagement. Educators utilizing creative teaching methods, technology, and student-centered approaches facilitate active learning and sustained engagement (Lee & Hannafin 2016).

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study is focused in investigating the effects of AI on mechanical technology education students' academic performance in Milling Machine in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research investigated:

1. Effects of AI package on mechanical technology education students' academic performance

when taught cutting tools used in milling processes

2. Effects of AI package on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught direction of cutting rotation
3. Effects of AI package on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught types of milling operation

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught cutting tools used in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
3. What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught types of milling operation in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught cutting tools used in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught types of milling operation in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quasi-experimental design. It is a quasi-experimental study because the study was a non-randomized control group, pre-test post-test design. The independent variable was manipulated by the researchers under controlled conditions. The study exposed the experimental group to treatment. Intact classes were used for the research. The population of the study comprised 193 Year I-IV mechanical technology education students in the three tertiary institutions in Rivers State that offer the programme, namely: Rivers State University (RSU), Port Harcourt, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE), Port Harcourt and Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in affiliation with University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Out of the four levels, the researcher selected Year III for the study with a population of 83 students. This is because, they have spent more than two years in the programme and they were not occupied with project work, hence they were available for the research. The selected population was manageable; therefore, the entire population was adopted for the study. The researcher collected data for the study using teacher made test containing forty-five items. The teacher made test was two multiple choice type of teacher made test, one for pre-test and the other for post-test. Two teaching strategies were used in the instruction delivery during this experiment. The two strategies were conventional strategy (lecture method) whereby whiteboard was used in teaching, and the AI package. The control group were taught with the conventional strategy while the experimental group were taught with the AI package. The teaching period lasted for two weeks. Content appropriateness of the instruments were face and content validated by two expert (lecturers) from department of Technology Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, the reliability of the instrument was established using test re-test method. Copies of the instrument were administered to 12-year III mechanical technology education students in the Department of Vocational and Technology Education. Faculty of Education, Niger

Delta University who were not part of the population. The data achieved were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The reliability coefficient achieved was .78. In order to collect data for the study, the researcher taught the experimental and control groups with two different lesson plans. The experimental group was taught using the AI package while the control groups were taught with lecture method. From the lesson plan the pre-test and post-test questions were constructed to collect data. The pre-test questions were administered to the two groups first before teaching process. The post test questions were administered on the two groups after teaching has taken place. The data collected were used for data analysis. The data was analyzed using mean to answer the research questions and to ascertain the homogeneity of responses with Standard Deviation. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistics were used to test the hypotheses at .05 levels of significance. If mean gain is positive, the experimental method was regarded

as positive; else it was regarded as negative. Also, if calculated p-value is less than a .05 level of significance, H0 was rejected. On the other hand, if p-value is greater than a .05 level of significance, H0 was accepted.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSION

Research Question 1

What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught cutting tools used in milling processes in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Answer to Research Question One is presented in **Table 1**

Table 1; Mean scores of Students' Academic Performance in cutting tools used in milling processes when taught with AI Package

Category	N	Pre-test \bar{X}_1	Pre-test SD ₁	Post-text \bar{X}_2	Post- test SD ₂	Mean difference	Mean gain	Decision
Control group	41	43.73	7.67	63.14	7.59	19.41		
Experimental groups	42	44.45	5.63	64.91	7.41	20.00	1.05	Positive

Source: Field Study, 2025 (Note: n= Sample Size)

Table 1. Show that the pre-test means and standard deviation for experimental group were 44.45 and 5.63 while that of control group were 43.73 and 7.67 respectively. The mean and standard deviation scores of pre-tests for the two groups revealed that students in experimental group did better on the pre- test than those in the control group. Similarly, the post-test mean and standard deviation for experimental group were 64, 91 and 7.41 while that of control group were 63.14 and 7.59 respectively.

This revealed that students in experimental group did better on the post-test than those in the control group. Furthermore, the mean gain between the two groups was 1.05 which shows positive result; hence the experimental method was effective. Therefore, students taught types of cutting tools used in milling processes with AI package performed better than those taught with the use of chalkboard, (lecture) Method.

Research Question 2

What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic

performance when taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Answer to Research Question One is presented in

Table 2; Mean scores of Students' Academic Performance in direction of cutting rotation in milling processes when taught with AI Package

Category	N	Pre-test \bar{X}_1	Pre-test SD ₁	Post-test \bar{X}_2	Post-test SD ₂	Mean difference	Mean gain	Decision
Control group	41	44.63	9.04	67.43	9.49	22.87	12.93	Positive
Experimental groups	42	43.14	7.65	78.80	8.78	35.80		

Source: Field Study, 2025 (Note: n= Sample Size)

Table 2. Show that the pre-test mean and standard deviation for experimental group were 43.14 and 7.65 while that of control group were 44.63 and 9.04 respectively. The mean and standard deviation scores of pre-tests for the two groups revealed that students in control group did better on the pre- test than those in the experimental group. Similarly, the post-test mean and standard deviation for experimental group were 78.80 and 8.78 while that of control group were 67.43 and 9.49 respectively. This revealed that students in experimental group

did better on the post-test than those in the control group. Furthermore, the mean gain between the two groups was 12.93 which shows positive result; hence the experimental method was effective. Therefore, students taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes with AI package performed better than those taught with the use of chalkboard, (lecture) Method.

Research Question 3

What are the effects of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught types of milling operation in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Answer to Research Question One is presented in Table 3

Table 3; Mean scores of Students' Academic Performance in types of milling operation when taught with AI Package

Category	N	Pre-test \bar{X}_1	Pre-test SD ₁	Post-text \bar{X}_2	Post- test SD ₂	Mean difference	Mean gain	Decision
Control group	41	46.87	9.91	70.03	11.35	23.16		
Experimental groups	42	45.67	10.80	70.93	11.46	25.26	2.10	Positive

Source: Field Study, 2025 (Note: n= Sample Size)

Table 3. Show that the pre-test mean and standard deviation for experimental group were 45.67 and 10.80 while that of control group were 46.87 and 9, 91 respectively. The mean and standard deviation scores of pre-tests for the two groups revealed that students in control group did better on the pre- test than those in the experimental group. Similarly, the post-test mean and standard deviation for experimental group were 70, 93 and 11.46 while that of control group were 70.03 and 11.35 respectively. This revealed that students in experimental group

did better on the post-test than those in the control group. Furthermore, the mean gain between the two groups was 2.10 which shows positive result; hence the experimental method was effective. Therefore, students taught types of milling operation with AI package performed better than those taught with the use of chalkboard, (lecture) Method.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught cutting tools used in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

Table 3.1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) cutting tools used in milling process

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1633.101 ^a	2	816.550	22.055	.000
Intercept	2208.497	1	2208.497	59.653	.000
VAR00007	14.239	1	14.239	.385	.537
VAR00008	1597.712	1	1597.712	43.155	.000
Error	2961.815	80	37.023		
Total	342518.000	83			
Corrected Total	4594.916	82			

From Table 4.1, F-cal is 22.05 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught cutting tools used in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers

State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

Table 5.1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for direction of cutting rotation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1905.716 ^a	2	952.858	13.557	.000
Intercept	5907.855	1	5907.855	84.057	.000
VAR00010	741.700	1	741.700	10.553	.002
VAR00011	993.880	1	993.880	14.141	.000
Error	5622.693	80	70.284		
Total	348393.000	83			
Corrected Total	7528.410	82			

From Table 5.1, F-cal is 13.55 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using

AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught types of milling operation in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies.

Table 6.1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Scores in types of milling operation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1149.447 ^a	2	574.723	4.962	.009
Intercept	10360.854	1	10360.854	89.460	.000
VAR00013	3.004	1	3.004	.026	.872
VAR00014	1149.205	1	1149.205	9.923	.002
Error	9265.276	80	115.816		
Total	422734.000	83			
Corrected Total	10414.723	82			

From Table 6.1, F-cal is 4.96 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught types of milling machine operation in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with conventional teaching strategies.

MAJOR FINDINGS

From the analysis of data collected in respect to this study, the following findings were made:

1. Students in the experimental group taught cutting tools used in milling processes in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using Artificial Intelligence package did better than those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies with a mean gain of 1.05
2. Students in the experimental group who were taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes with AI package performed better than those taught with the use of chalkboard, (lecture) Method with a mean gain of 12.93
3. Students in the experimental group taught types of milling operation in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using Artificial Intelligence package did better than those taught with conventional (lecture) teaching strategies with a mean gain of 2.10

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of the results on the effect of AI package on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught cutting tools used in milling processes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, showed that students in the experimental group did better than those taught with chalkboard and charts. Also, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught cutting tools used in milling processes mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State using AI package and those taught with whiteboard and chart. This is in conformity with Popenici and Kerr (2017) who posited that artificial Intelligence is advancing faster in the services and educational systems. It is geared toward automated individualized education to support students' academic performance at all levels of education through virtual engagement at the student's convenience and time.

The analysis of the results on the effect of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught direction of cutting rotation in milling processes in mechanical technology education in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, showed that students who were taught using AI package performed better than those taught with chalkboard and charts. Also, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students in the two groups. This is in line with Seo, et al (2021) who asserted that in the area of education, Artificial intelligence (AI) systems assist effectively in online/self-learning and teaching, automating instructors' mundane activities; personalizing learning for students; and adaptive evaluation.

The analysis of the results on the effect of AI packages on mechanical technology education students' academic performance when taught types of milling operation in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, showed that students who were taught using AI package performed better than those taught with chalkboard and charts. Also, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students in the two groups. This is in line with (Wang and Liu (2021)) who stated that the adoption of AI in education offers a promising pathway to personalized learning and improved academic performance.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations were put forward based on the findings:

1. Government should train lecturers on the development and use of Artificial Intelligence package so that they can be able to use this strategy in teaching since it has proven to be effective.
2. Artificial Intelligence package strategy should be included in the mechanical technology education curriculum so that lecturers can adopt it for effective theoretical teaching.
3. Mechanical technology education lecturers should adopt the use of AI package strategy when teaching topics that does not necessary require practical activities so as to enhance students' academic performance in mechanical technology education programmes in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

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